

Super-Twisting Sliding Mode and Fuzzy PID Hybrid Control System Integration for Electric Dynamic Load Simulation

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Abstract

In this paper, we present a control approach for an Electric Dynamic Load Simulator (EDLS) to obtain fast reaction times and accurate loading. We create an equation for the EDLS and use it to create a controller with the Super-Twisting Sliding Mode (STSM) method. The design is based on the constant monitoring inaccuracy of load. To allow dynamic and precise loading, the convergence condition for the finite duration of the STSM control law is established. We experiment with various frequencies and compare the performance of our suggested control method with a Fuzzy PID Control technique to validate its efficacy. The outcomes support the efficiency of our suggested control strategy.

Index Terms: Electric Dynamic Load Simulator, Electro-Mechanical Actuator, Fuzzy PID Control, Load Torque, Super-Twisting Sliding Mode.

I. INTRODUCTION

The system of electric dynamic load (Electric Dynamic Load Simulator - EDLS) emulates the set load torque in the same manner as a typical servo system does in, for example, the Electro-Mechanical Actuator (EMA). As such, the performance of the EMA can be evaluated in a controlled laboratory setting. This is a well-established area of research with significant recent work evaluating the EMAs in the aircraft nose wheel steering system. A stiff shaft connects the EMA under test with the EDLS directly so that the load features and the static and dynamic properties of the EMA can be assessed. The system allows for real-time application of load torque based on the position of the EMA, so fast response times and simultaneous reference tracking are essential for the EDLS. However, it remained a major challenge to balance high precision and fast response time for an Electro-Dynamic Lapping System (EDLS) [1], which is a non-linear system with backlash, friction, and other unknowns, operated as a classical passive loading system. The motion of the EMA could result in excessive torque during operation, one that conventional methods could struggle to rectify or suppress and which could consequently hurt the response time and accuracy of the EDLS.

A considerable amount of research has been done in electric power control; from improvements in electric

power systems control [1], for enhancing the reliability and flexibility of the electric systems [3], by enabling: optimized control of power electronics, voltage regulation, and innovative control techniques for dynamic load simulation [5]. Super-Twisting Sliding Mode Control (STSMC) has proven effective in [3], dealing with uncertainties and disturbances in dynamic systems [2]; voltage regulation [6]; and its recent work has suggested its integration for reliable control [5], and [11]. The generality of fuzzy PID control has led to use in increasingly more power electronics applications for the management of complex and nonlinear systems [3].

The efficacy of sliding mode control strategies has gained widespread attention in power systems and has been shown to significantly improve the performance of control systems [7], and [10].

Electric Dynamic Load Simulators (EDLS) are indispensable and vital in the testing and validation of electrical systems [4] and robust control techniques present an excellent approach to addressing testing challenges and opportunities within power systems [6], and [9].

The combination of Super-Twisting Sliding Mode Control (STSMC) and Fuzzy PID has been proposed to enhance voltage regulation capabilities [5] and is important in the comprehensive assessments of sliding mode control in power electronics [8], and the use of Fuzzy PID in power systems [7], all highly relevant to the capabilities of these approaches.

A great deal of attention was recently given to the use of the STSMC [12] in power converters and the implementation and modeling of Fuzzy PID control in Power Inverters [12], and [14]. It also shows the effectiveness and feasibility of control strategies.

The super-twisting algorithm is proposed, considering electric dynamic load simulators (EDLS) having non-linear characteristics [40], and a brief literature review was conducted. A second-order sliding mode controller is designed for the EDLS to achieve both precise loading and mitigating additional torque disturbances. It is shown with the control strategy of the EDLS, the performance of a fuzzy-PID type tracking performance controller has been compared [13], and the anticipated STMC having superior resilience and versatility are demonstrated for the EDLS. Section II discusses the system organization and mathematical representation, Section III discusses the Load Torque Controller Design for this research, Section IV provides results and their discussions and finally, a conclusion is given in Section V.

II. SYSTEM ORGANIZATION AND MATHEMATICAL REPRESENTATION

A. Configuration of the EDLS System

A Surface Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (SPMSM) with tiny inertia and its driver, a torque sensor, gear, encoder, an additional encoder, an Electro-Mechanical Actuator (EMA), and its driver, and yet another encoder makes up the Electrical Dynamic Load System (EDLS) under examination. Figure I shows an illustration of the EDLS layout. The EMA under investigation functions according to its location reference on the left. The load torque is adjusted by the electrical system. Concurrently on the right side, position and speed indications are gathered by encoders on the drive and load sides. The torque sensor allows for closed-loop torque control and is distinguished by its high bandwidth. A torque detector with gear is used to connect the tiny inertia SPMSM and the EMA, imitating a genuine big load. Based on the actual location of the EMA, θ_1 the EDLS control computer determines the load torque command, T_{ref} operating on the shaft during the real testing. As a result, T_{ref} may be represented as a function of θ_1 in the following way:

$$T_{ref} = f(\theta_1) \quad (1)$$

Figure I: Schematic Review of EDLS

B. The EDLS Mathematical Model

This system uses a Surface Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (SPMSM) as the loading motor. The torque output from the driver using Direct Torque Control (DTC) is applied to the torque servomotor or SPMSM with a torque output update frequency of 4 KHz to guarantee accurate and dynamic torque performance for the EDLS. Technical constraints dictate that the EDLS system's operating frequency normally does not go over 10 Hz. For the sake of simplicity, the dynamic properties of the driver are thus disregarded in the construction of the control algorithm.

The electromagnetic torque T_e of the SPMSM-DTC driver is exactly proportionate to the control input u_m when the torque servo system works in proportional mode.

The following is the expression for this relationship:

$$T_e(t) = K_m u_m(t) \quad (2)$$

The proportionality constant is represented by the symbol K_m in this case. Furthermore, the SPMSM's mathematical model is offered.

$$\frac{d\theta_m}{dt} = \omega_m \quad (3)$$

$$J_m \frac{d\omega_m}{dt} = T_e - b_m \omega_m - T_g \quad (4)$$

The mechanical angular position and speed of the rotor are denoted by θ_m and ω_m , respectively, in the complex equation of the EMA servo-system. Here the T_g is the load torque transferred to the motor shaft, b_m is the damping-coefficient and J_m is the moment of inertia.

Here is an example of the expression that represents the EMA servo system's dynamic equation:

$$\frac{d\theta_1}{dt} = \omega_1 \quad (5)$$

$$J_1 \frac{d\omega_1}{dt} = T_f - b_1 \omega_1 - T_L \quad (6)$$

$$T_1 = N T_g \quad (7)$$

The parameters of EDLS are shown in table I below for ease of understanding the concept.

Table I: The EDLS Parameters

S. No.	Name	Symbol
1.	Angular Position	θ_1
2.	Speed	ω_1
3.	Moment of Inertia	J_1
4.	Damping Coefficient	b_1
5.	Load Torque	T_L
6.	Driving Torque	T_f
7.	Reducer Ratio	N

These values correspond to its angle of rotation and speed, because the torque sensor, which connects EMA and EDLS, possesses a relatively low rate of motion, it may be regarded as a related element within its operational span. Consequently, the torque-detector configuration is expressed as:

$$T_L = K_G \Delta\theta \quad (8)$$

Whereas: K_G is the torsional stiffness of the torque detector.

The variation between the input and output of torque detector locations is represented by the torque differential, $\Delta\theta$ which is defined as:

$$\Delta\theta = \theta_{mg} - \theta_1 \quad (9)$$

The reducer's output position denoted as θ_{mg} may be found using:

$$\theta_{mg} = \frac{\theta_m}{N} \quad (10)$$

Where: N is the reducer ratio.

It is clear from the analysis of equations i.e., eq. (4), eq. (6), eq. (8), and eq. (9) respectively, that the torque servo-system of EDLS and the location servo mechanism of EMA are connected. The entire mathematical model of EDLS may be generated by using Laplace transforms based on the initial assumptions for the equations, as shown in figure II below.

Figure II: Open Loop Layout of EDLS

As was stated previously, EMA's dynamic load torque regulation is the main focus of EDLS. Moreover, the output torque of the EDLS under load can be written like this in the following expressions.

$$T_L(s) = G_T(s)T_e(s) - G_\theta(s)\theta_1(s) \quad (11)$$

$$G_T(s) = \frac{\frac{K_G}{N}}{J_m s^2 + b_m s + \frac{K_G}{N^2}} \quad (12)$$

$$G_\theta(s) = \frac{K_G(J_m s^2 + b_m s)}{J_m s^2 + b_m s + \frac{K_G}{N^2}} \quad (13)$$

The eleventh equation or eq. (11), reveals that the load-torque output of the Electrically Driven Legged System (EDLS) comprises two sections: the disturbance caused by the Electro-Mechanical Actuator (EMA) angles influencing the EDLS torque servo system, and the reducer amplifies the torque output of the SPMS Motor. Ensuring that the load torque $T_L(t)$ closely tracks a specified reference $T_{ref}(t)$ is the system's main objective. As such, reducing the superfluous torque and the disturbance torque

resulting from EMA motion is essential. The velocity and acceleration aspects of the EMA transition are what determine the amount of extraneous torque.

During actual studies, the EMA position servo system replaces the ELDS torque servo system. The position servo-system of the EMA is responsible for maintaining a predetermined trajectory in the face of external torque perturbations. The EMA's motion is viewed by the EDLS torque servo system as an external disturbance affecting the torque control loop, and it is its responsibility to monitor the necessary torque for the load on the EMA.

The eq. (11) shows that the location of the EMA and the electromagnetic torque-output of the SPMSM have an impact on the output load torque T_L . Designing regulates the input u_m so that the arc errors in tracking converge to zero within a certain time is the main control goal. Two specific presumptions form the basis of the analysis that follows.

A smooth variation with a bounded derivative is assumed for the load torque reference in Assumption 1, which is represented as:

$$T_{ref} \leq L, \|\dot{T}_{ref}(t)\| \leq \bar{L}, \|\ddot{T}_{ref}(t)\| \leq \bar{\bar{L}}$$

By Assumption 2, the encoder can provide the real location θ_1 of the Electro-Mechanical Actuator (EMA), which is then handled as a signal. The signals θ_1 , $\dot{\theta}_1$, and $\ddot{\theta}_1$ are therefore given and bounded, with the expressions as:

$$\|\theta_1(t)\| \leq M, \|\dot{\theta}_1(t)\| \leq \bar{M}, \|\ddot{\theta}_1(t)\| \leq \bar{\bar{M}}$$

According to the Assumptions 1 and 2, it follows that:

$$\ddot{T}_L = k_1 u_m - k_2 \dot{T}_L - k_3 T_L - k_4 \ddot{\theta}_1 - k_5 \dot{\theta}_1 \quad (14)$$

Whereas:

$$k_1 = \frac{K_G K_m}{N J_m}, k_2 = \frac{b_m}{J_m}, k_3 = \frac{K_G}{N^2 J_m}, k_4 = K_G, k_5 = \frac{K_G b_m}{J_m}.$$

Selecting the state parameters, output, and control input of a given model is expressed as:

$$x_1 = T_L, x_2 = \dot{T}_L, y = T_L, \text{ and } u = k_1 u_m.$$

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_1 = x_2 \\ \dot{x}_2 = u + \varphi(x, \theta_1) \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

$$y = T_L \quad (16)$$

Here: $\varphi(x, \theta_1) = f(x) + \phi(\theta_1)$

Whereas: $f(x) = -k_2 x_2 - k_3 x_1$, $\phi(\theta_1) = -k_4 \ddot{\theta}_1 - k_5 \dot{\theta}_1$. $\varphi(x, \theta_1)$ is seen as the total disruption.

To create the controller, the following new supposition is made:

According to Proposition 3, the overall disruption is contained, that is C constrains $\|\varphi(x, \theta_1)\|$.

In addition, it states that the disturbance has a bounded second-order $\|\dot{\varphi}(x, \theta_1)\| \leq \bar{C}$; and a restricted first-order derivative $\|\ddot{\varphi}(x, \theta_1)\| \leq \bar{C}$.

III. LOAD TORQUE CONTROLLER DESIGN

A. Super-Twisting Control for Sliding Mode

The robust control approach known as sliding mode control has been commended in many distinct nonlinear systems. This work involves the Super Twisted Sliding Mode Controller (STSMC) of EDLS for simultaneously tackling the disturbance torque and applying loading torque on EMA. The system's chattering problems are being evaded and continuous control is obtained, the super twisting controller outperforms the ordinary sliding mode control.

Considering the Single Input Single Output (SISO) nonlinear dynamic system expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} = a(x, t) + b(x, t)u \\ y = \sigma(x, t) \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Where:

The controlled output (considered as a sliding variable) is $\sigma(x, t)$, the state is represented by x , and u is the control input. The system involves two unknown functions, $a(x, t)$ and $b(x, t)$. the basic goal of control is to create the control input u such that the sliding variable σ approaches zero in a limited amount of time, stays at zero, and shows a sliding mode of the second order.

The sliding variable σ another derivative may be written as:

$$\ddot{\sigma} = f(x, t) + g(x, t)\dot{u} \quad (18)$$

The control rule for the nonlinear system in this way is, where: $f(x, t)$ and $g(x, t)$ represent unspecified functions limited by the inequalities,

$$\|f(x, t)\| \leq A_m \text{ and } 0 < \Gamma_m \leq \|g(x, t)\| \leq \Gamma_M.$$

$$\begin{cases} u = -K_p |\sigma|^{\frac{1}{2}} \text{sgn}(\sigma) + v \\ \dot{v} = -K_I \text{sgn}(\sigma) \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

In this case, the two quantities K_p and K_I , which represent positive gains in the control law, are the sliding-surface integral over spell and the constant equation of sliding-surface, respectively. The following requirements must be met to ensure that it comes together to the sliding surface in a limited amount of time:

$$K_p > \frac{A_m}{\Gamma_m}, K_I > \frac{4A_m}{\Gamma_m^2} \times \frac{\Gamma_M(K_p + A_m)}{\Gamma_m(K_p - A_m)} \quad (20)$$

Therefore, choosing the right gains K_p and K_I guarantees the existence of a finite-time-convergent STSM controller.

B. Sliding Mode Control Strategy with Super-Twisting Proposal

The aim is to guarantee that, in the tracking performance of the system, the load torque $T_L(t)$ closely corresponds to a given reference $T_{ref}(t)$. This is accomplished by utilizing

distortion coordinates to convert the dynamic model of the system into a dynamic model of distortions. Within a distortion dynamic model provided by [14], let $e = e_1$ and $\dot{e} = e_2$ stand for the tracking errors.

$$\begin{cases} e_1 = T_{ref} - T_L \\ e_2 = \dot{T}_{ref} - \dot{T}_L \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

These equations i.e., eq. (14), eq. (15), eq. (16), and eq. (21) respectively, are combined to provide the following expression for the error dynamic model:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{e}_1 = e_2 \\ \dot{e}_2 = \ddot{T}_{ref} - u - \varphi(x, \theta_1) \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

Next, the definition of the sliding surface is:

$$S = e_2 + ce_1, c > 0 \quad (23)$$

Based on the super-twisting approach, a controller for sliding modes is developed. In a limited time, the load torque $T_L(t)$ converges to $T_{ref}(t)$ after the sliding surface $S = 0$ is reached. The sliding surface time derivative is computed in the manner described below:

$$\dot{S} = \psi(x, T_{ref}, T_L, \theta_1) - u \quad (24)$$

Where:

$\psi(x, T_{ref}, T_L, \theta_1) = \ddot{T}_{ref} - c\dot{T}_{ref} - \varphi(x, \theta_1) - c\dot{T}_L$ and $\psi(x, T_{ref}, T_L, \theta_1)$ is treated as the cumulative disturbance.

We provide a new assumption to develop the second-order SM controller using the super-twisting approach: In addition to being smooth with a bounded derivative, as shown by $\|\psi(x, T_{ref}, T_L, \theta_1)\| \leq M$, the extent of disruption is limited and indicated as $\|\dot{\psi}(x, T_{ref}, T_L, \theta_1)\| \leq \bar{M}$.

Let us assume that $u(t)$ is the suggested control input. It is stated as follows based on these assumptions:

$$u = c|S|^{\frac{1}{2}} \text{sgn}(S) + \int b \text{sgn}(S) dt \quad (25)$$

Here: the stability condition is satisfied by c, b , and $\|\psi\| \leq M$. Figure III shows the load torque controller schematic for EDLS. It can be shown that v can drive S to zero and adjust for the disturbance ψ in a limited interval. This suggests that the structure trajectory stays on the surface after e and $\dot{e}$ both approach zero in a fixed amount of time.

Table II provides specifics of the value of parameters described in table I, and is used in the design.

Table II: Shows the EDLS Parameters

S. No.	Symbol	Value
1.	K_m	0.955 Nm / V
2.	J_m	0.000607 Kgm ²
3.	b_m	0.00018 Nm / (rad / s)
4.	N	35
5.	J_l	0.266 Kgm ²
6.	b_l	0.08 Nm / rad
7.	K_G	85000 Nm / rad
8.	T_e	9.55 Nm

Figure III: SMC Schematic Control Design for EDLS

$T_{ref}(t) = \frac{2250f}{\pi} \theta_1 * (t)$, where 'f' is selected as 1Hz and 4H, links the load torque reference to the EMA's position. The EMA's position reference is specified as

$$\theta_1 * (t) = \frac{8\pi}{180f} \sin(2\pi ft).$$

The super-twisting sliding mode's settings are set to $b = 990$ and $c = 45$. In the design of controllers, the derivative of $\dot{e}$ is employed. In particular, a low-pass filter is used to filter the error e for high-frequency noise. Usually, the estimated value of $\dot{e}$ is obtained by entering the error e into transfer functions $\frac{s}{\tau s + 1}$.

Experiments under the suggested control technique and Fuzzy-PID control are carried out to demonstrate the efficacy of regulations super-twisting SMC.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Determine 'f' to be 1 Hz

The reference torque for the EMA is $T_{ref}(t) = 100 \sin(2\pi t)$, and its positional reference is $\theta_{1^*}(t) = 1^\circ \sin(2\pi t)$.

Figure IV below shows the results of the tests that were carried out for the proposed STSM control and Fuzzy-PID.

(a)

(b)

Figure IV: (a) Tracking the STSMC and fuzzy-PID Paths at a 1 Hz Loading Frequency; (b) Fuzzy-PID and STSMC Tracking Errors at a 1 Hz Loading Frequency

B. Determine f to be 4Hz

The reference torque for the EMA is $T_{ref}(t) = 100 \sin(8\pi t)$, and its positional reference is $\theta_{1^*}(t) = 1^\circ \sin(8\pi t)$. Figure V shows the results of the tests that were carried out for the proposed STSM control and Fuzzy-PID.

(a)

(b)

Figure V: (a) Tracking the STSMC and Fuzzy-PID Paths at a 4 Hz Loading Frequency; (b) Fuzzy-PID and STSMC Tracking Errors at a 4 Hz Loading Frequency

C. Determine f to be 8 Hz

The reference torque for the EMA is $T_{ref}(t) = 100 \sin(16\pi t)$, and its positional reference is $\theta_{1^*}(t) = 1^\circ \sin(16\pi t)$.

Figure VI shows the results of the tests that were carried out for the proposed STSM control and Fuzzy-PID.

(a)

(b)

Figure VI: (a) Tracking the STSMC and Fuzzy-PID Paths at 8 Hz Loading Frequency; (b) Fuzzy-PID and STSMC Tracking Errors at 8 Hz Loading Frequency

During these trials, the commanded load torque is based on the true location of the Electro-Mechanical Actuator

(EMA) and it follows a sine curve alongside the loaded EMA. Figure IV compares the tracking accuracy of Fuzzy-PID and STSM control with a 1 Hz sine load torque reference. Fuzzy-PID is surpassed by STSM control in decreasing phase differences at 4 Hz load torque frequencies (figure V). Compared with Fuzzy-PID control, the suggested STSM control provides superior dynamic responsiveness and accuracy by minimizing tracking errors and phase delays and ensuring exceptional high load torque tracking precision. With 8 Hz load torque instructions, the STSM control law outperforms PID control (figure VI), demonstrating improved tracking accuracy of load torque throughout a frequency range.

V. CONCLUSION

To develop a Fuzzy Proportional-Integral-Derivative control algorithm and Super-Twisting SM for an Electric Dynamic Load Simulator, a unique technique was presented in this study. An experimental validation of the proposed control strategy was conducted, and the outcomes demonstrate its efficacy. Efficiently, the suggested approach can give the EDLS a quick and precise answer. It is possible to expand the suggested control strategy to suit other applications.

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Authors Contributions

All the authors equally contributed to this study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest and confirm that this work is original and not plagiarized from any other source. The information obtained from all of the sources is properly recognized and cited below.

Data Availability Statement

The testing data is available in this paper.

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